

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS, AND INFORMATICS

STUDY AND MODELING BEHAVIOR OF QUANTUM SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the problems of studying and researching the behavior of quantum systems. The proposed approach to research is based on the accumulated experience of studying the interactions of multidimensional dynamic systems exhibiting chaotic behavior within the framework of the Open System. The work focuses on visualization and visual analysis of the results of modeling systems interaction processes. Considering the difference between quantum computing algorithms and traditional, classical ones, it is proposed to use non-standard thinking for their modeling and simulation.

Keywords: Quantum informatics, nonlinear dynamics, quantum chaos, Poincare recurrence, Lyapunov exponents, Visual Thinking.

1. Introduction

Quantum informatics is a modern and rapidly developing discipline based on the ideas of quantum physics, quantum mechanics, quantum computing and modern mathematics. The increased interest in quantum informatics is justified by the prospects that it promises when using it in the study of a wide range of problems in physics and computer science [1-8].

As for the possibilities of processing, visualization, analysis, and the use of new knowledge on the analysis of measurement information, new horizons are opening up for a creative initiative.

Starting to study the features of the quantum world and quantum informatics, we want to apply the knowledge gained to the analysis of various sections of physics and computer science theory.

2. Quantum informatics in the educational process

The foundation of quantum mechanics and computer science has been the subject of many works by well-known researchers and scientists [3,4,6-10]. The most significant and relevant parts of this field of knowledge include: "quantum computer", "quantum algorithms", "quantum computing", "quantum information" and "quantum cryptography". The performance and computing power of classic computers in recent years have developed exclusively due to modern technologies, which increased these indicators due to an increase in the clock frequency and the number of operations performed per clock cycle. Since 1994, when Peter Shore presented the rationale for the power of a quantum computer compared to a classical one, the situation has radically changed. At first, simple elements of a quantum computer appeared, a quantum "qubit", and then quantum computers. Due to the parallelization of the operations performed by generating entangled quantum states, it is possible to achieve advantages in modeling complex dynamic processes. Interesting prospects open up in the field of cyber security, quantum cryptography, in the field of artificial quantum intelligence, decision making with incomplete data, and much more. Physical foundations, device, principle of operation, components, software, fields of

application, research directions and many topical issues for the study of quantum systems can be found in [8-12].

To understanding the distinguishing features of quantum computers in comparison with the classical one, we can say that they significantly differ from them in such specific features as:

- quantum computers operate with qubits of information;
- information in quantum computers in the process of calculation is used in the quantum form "superposition" in the form of mixed zeros and ones, but the result will be presented in the traditionally familiar form of binary values;
- unlike classical computers, in quantum computers, the processor and memory are a single whole, and qubits are the keepers of information;
- the entry and reading of information from qubits today is done using lasers and a magnetic field;
- the purpose of quantum computers in the use of their capabilities in modeling complex processes;
- qubits having the ability to be simultaneously in all admissible states allow parallel to sort through all states, that is, solution options, etc. [8-12].

All of the above suggests that today the use of quantum computers is limited to solving scientific problems and their use in everyday life, due to their complexity and specific capabilities, is not considered.

As you know, quantum computational informatics, in contrast to the classical binary, operates when performing calculations with quantum-mechanical phenomena as superposition and entanglement, and the use of the possibility of parallel processing of information in addition increases the computational ability. Presentation of information in the register of a quantum computer in qubits against binary bits in the usual allows you to represent and process all possible data states at the same time.

The objects of computation and modeling of processes using quantum computers can be physics, measurement technology, medicine, cryptography, etc. for which the computational capabilities of today's classical computers are a deterrent.

The principle of representation and processing of information by qubits differs from the usual methods. So, for example, a two-qubit gateway allows you to process all four combinations of 0 and 1 at the same time and these are not all the distinguishing features of

quantum computing. An example of the representation of 3 bits of information in the registers of a classical and quantum computer is a confirmation of this (Figure 1).

Figure 1. An example of the representation of 3 bits of information in the classical and quantum register.

When studying quantum systems, interesting opportunities are provided for observing the phenomena of information transfer (teleportation), superposition of qubits, observer effect, and other distinctive features.

As a result of what has been said, we can conclude that, in contrast to classical methods, quantum computing requires the use of non-standard thinking and comprehension of what is happening.

The Schrödinger differential equation is a wave function that describes the state and probability of finding particles in a limited space [13-17]. The motion and

state of a quantum particle was studied by the method of discretization of its energy, and the space-time description of the motion of a particle in a force field made it possible to describe its quantum state.

As you know, the world around us, as an Open System, is conditionally represented as shown in the figure below:

Figure 2. Information space of the Open System.

In the traditional sense, the macro world is classical, and the micro world is discrete or quantum. The complexity of studying quantum systems by methods of mathematical modeling or conducting physical experiments lies in the fact that the methods used by us in the study of the macro world are not applicable here.

Another difficulty lies in the difference between classical and quantum informatics. Here we are confronted with quantum entanglement, which is at the heart of quantum informatics. The lack of correlation between classical research approaches and quantum ones does not allow using accumulated experience for

their study and research. However, we can mathematically model the behavior of a quantum system, although this will not be an easy task [18-21].

3. Quantum informatics in scientific research

You must admit that not a single quantum system can function in isolation from the surrounding reality. The study of the dynamics of the behavior of quantum systems in the framework of the Open System is an urgent task of our time [2,13-16,22-27]. When modeling complex processes, analyzing and controlling their dynamics, enumeration of possible states and evolution of

a development scenario can be significantly accelerated by the use of quantum algorithms.

As is known, the study of quantum entanglement, a quantum-mechanical phenomenon, is performed using wave functions. The essence of the problem is that when describing the properties of physical reality, it is necessary to take into account:

- until the measurement is made, it is impossible to talk about the properties,
- the measuring process, being active in its effect, affects the measured system.

Therefore, before the measurement process is initialized, the system may be in a superposition of several potential states, however, everything changes when we measure, as a result of which the superposition is removed and the system occupies a specific position. This phenomenon must be considered when taking measurements [21-27].

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The principle of representation and processing of information by qubits differs from the usual methods. So, for example, a two-qubit gateway allows you to process all four combinations of 0 and 1 at the same time.

Given the fact that an increase in the number of qubits leads to a doubling of their combinations, this exponential increase in the number of combinations with the possibility of parallel processing can significantly increase productivity.

If you try to imagine the immediate goals of quantum informatics, you can note problems such as:

- modeling of complex physical, chemical and biological processes;
- more accurate and error-free processing of measurement data;
- optimization in various fields of industry;
- artificial Intelligence;
- training systems; and other information media.

The functioning of a quantum open system takes place in a rather complex environment. In this case, manifestations of chaos in the properties of quantum systems are noted, as well as the influence of disturbing influences, as well as their intensity. The study of dynamic transport processes in quantum systems is inextricably linked with the study and consideration of the impact on their behavior of such effects as chimeric states, quantum fluctuations, synchronization phenomena in the form of coherent and incoherent states, quantum Levy walks, fractal scaling, observer influence, control effect of the researcher, etc. [21,25-27].

When a quantum system interacts with a medium with a change in its dynamics, a memory effect (non-Markovian dynamic) is manifested. In our opinion, an important fragment of studies of the behavior of quantum systems is the processes of transport and mixing. The behavior of a quantum system and the dynamics of its particles will be described both by the uncertainty principle and by the Schrödinger equation [13-16]. Studies of the evolution of the development of quantum systems have been the subject of many works of both analytical and numerical simulations [25,27]. An approximate structure of process research is presented in Figure 3 and covers a range of potential scenarios of impacts on a quantum system.

The structure covers the listed influential and disturbing influences on the quantum system, while noting the change in dynamics and the manifestation of memory during mixing. In the process of studying and controlling the behavior of a quantum system, importance is attached to measuring informative parameters that help classify ongoing changes in the behavior of the system and determine the development of its dynamics as a whole.

Importance is given to visualization and visual analysis of system parameters. Examples of potentially significant informative parameters can be noted: Lyapunov exponents, Finite Time Lyapunov Exponents (FTLE), Poincare recurrence, Tsallis entropy, system memory fragments, parameter of stability, etc.

Figure 3. The structure of the study of the behavior of a quantum system

Examples of organizing scenarios for studying the behavior of complex systems are the algorithms presented below.

The structure of the study of the behavior of multidimensional chaotic fractional systems developing within the framework of the Open System is shown in Figure 4 [25,27]:

Figure 4. The structure and components of interacting fractional-chaotic systems investigated within the framework of the scientific direction - Physics of Open Systems.

Legend:

fBm – fractional Brownian motion; **fLevy** – fractional Levy motion; **Imp** – impulsive function; **fCN** – fractional Colored noise; **P - W** – piecewise function; **fGn** – fractional Gaussian noise; **q - p** – quasi-periodic; **ch - q-p** – chaos – quasi-periodic; **ch-stoch** – chaos – stochastic; **ch - hyp-ch** – chaos – hyper-chaos; **hyp - ch - hyp** - hyper-chaos - chaos - hyper-chaos; **bifur** – bifurcation; **FTE** – fractional time evolution.

3.1. Algorithm for studying the behavior of a complex system

To implement the tasks presented in the block diagram, we will construct an algorithm for studying the interactions of the system with the outside world. One of the criteria for evaluating the observed processes is an approach called "Visual Thinking" [28-30]. Estimating the values of the calculated informative parameters of interacting systems, the researcher using visual arguments in the form of topology, texture, color palette, shape, and others, can reveal hidden fragments of ongoing processes. This is facilitated by visual information obtained from the analysis of Recurrent Diagrams, Finite Time Lyapunov Exponents, Attractors, Poincare recurrence and return time plots, Tsallis entropy and others.

To build an algorithm for studying processes in interacting systems, it is necessary to show their relationship and informative parameters. The mathematical

model of the algorithm for studying the interactions of complex systems, including the main qualitative indicators, has the form [25,27]:

$$s_q = \left[\left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N s_q(D^q x) + \frac{1-\hat{q}}{n} \prod_{i=1}^N s_q(D^q x) \right\} + GM \right]$$

Here S_q is the Tsallis entropy, $D^q x$ fractional-order nonlinear system, N - number of interacting systems, GM - generalized memory, n - is a given parameter.

Along with the calculated Lyapunov exponents, the value of the Tsallis entropy, the formula includes a memory index, which consists of two parts - "residual and real memory of a fractional order system. The Poincare return times and its recurrence characterize the memory of the system and its constituent parts. The importance of the system memory and its constituent parts is important in the study of the behavior of a dynamic system. Associated with the fractal dimension, fragments of memory carry information about the development, trends of the system, about reversible and irreversible processes. Thus, the loss of information determines the value of the entropy of the system.

The algorithm for organizing the coherent behavior of a complex system is shown in Figure 5 and presents the stages of analysis and control and interaction for the study of transient processes [25-27]:

Figure 5. Organization of the coherence behavior systems.

The presented algorithm is designed to analyze the processes of influence, mutual influence and the flow of transient processes in interacting systems. The effects of Chimera perturbations allow, in addition to those presented in Figure 6, to simulate potential scenarios in the Open System. Making a decision on the development of

the dynamics, trend and behavior of interacting systems that satisfies the researcher is based on the calculated parameters and arguments of Visual Thinking.

The result of the above algorithm for searching for a coherent state of interacting hyper-chaotic systems: Rabinovich-Fabrikant, fractional-order Chen, hyper chaotic Qi, Liu system and Chimera states as an influencing noise is shown in the figure below:

Figure 6. An example of the algorithm for finding satisfactory coherence (a), the value of the Tsallis entropy (b), the stability index (c), the Poincare distance matrix recurrent diagram (d).

As can be seen from the visualization of the results of modeling the interactions of complex systems, the Tsallis entropy and recurrent diagrams from nonlinear recurrent analysis were used. The presented information will be further used in the input level of the Re-

current Neural Network of the Deep Learning algorithm to analyze the controllability of complex interacting systems [15,24-27].

The experience of analytical-numerical modeling of interacting systems is considered in the context of

the applicability of such methods for setting up measurement experiments to control quantum systems.

4. Schrodinger equation and methods for studying quantum systems and processes

Of course, the application of chaos control theory to the study of the behavior of a quantum system is not always acceptable, since, unlike a chaotic system, quantum mechanics does not always have sensitivity to small perturbations, known as the "butterfly effect" and its other features.

Nevertheless, a mathematical description of the behavior of a chaotic system can be useful in modeling quantum physical processes accompanied by rigorous mathematical equations.

As noted above, quantum mechanics studies the wave nature of the motion of particles in the micro world. Research in quantum physics is inextricably linked with the theoretical physicist Erwin Schrödinger, who, through his experimental research, derived a generalized equation that postulates the laws of motion of particles in the macrocosm:

$$\begin{cases} \hbar|\dot{\psi}\rangle = -iH_0|\psi\rangle, |\psi\rangle \in \mathbb{S}^{2N-1} \\ |\psi(0)\rangle = |\psi_0\rangle, \end{cases}$$

this linear ODE is known as the Schrödinger equation describing the state vector of the particle. Here H_0 represents the Hamiltonian of the system.

In subsequent calculations, the values of the Planck constant \hbar equal to 1 are used [13-17].

To conduct experiments on the control of a quantum system, we are interested in the possibility of using available methods.

As for the control of the behavior of a quantum mechanical system, this is achieved by exposure to electromagnetic and other types of fields, the amount and degree of impact of which can be selected depending on the task of the study.

To model dynamic processes within the framework of the Open System, and to describe the behavior of quantum systems, the interaction Hamiltonian is used [13-17].

The perturbing action is applicable for the interaction on a quantum in a physical medium during various simulation experiments. The result of decomposition in a simplified format can be represented as:

$$\begin{cases} |\dot{\psi}\rangle = -i\left(H_0 + \sum_j u_j H_j\right)|\psi\rangle, |\psi\rangle \in \mathbb{S}^{2N-1} \\ |\psi(0)\rangle = |\psi_0\rangle \end{cases}$$

here H_j is the control Hamiltonian, which reflects the connections between its free levels H_0 , and u_j , the intensity of the action, and also reflects the parameters:

$$u_j \in [u_{j,\min}, u_{j,\max}] \subset \mathbb{R}$$

of the control actions.

Such control is sometimes called coherent, since it allows you to save the development of the vector.

5. Discussion

To study and modeling the behavior of quantum systems, as well as chaotic systems, mathematical

methods are used to formulate the processes taking place. However, it should be taken into account that complete analogy in the behavior of quantum and classical chaotic systems is not observed, and therefore additional research is necessary. In our opinion, the use of visual analysis with the development of visual thinking will partially fill this gap, and will also provide informative support for the sources and algorithms of the input and hidden layers of the Recurrent Neural Network of Deep Learning.

6. Conclusions

The article presented to our attention is devoted to an incomplete range of problems of studying, analysis and modeling the behavior of quantum systems within the framework of the Open System. Recalling the main provisions that distinguish the quantum world from the classical one, an excursion on the problems of quantum computing is given. As an example, structures and algorithms for the study of chaotic systems are presented, covering a wide range of problems of analysis, evaluation and control of their behavior. An algorithm for controlling the behavior of a complex system is presented, possible participants in the measurement experiment, such as noise effects and control effects, as well as the most informative controlled parameters are listed. Examples of analysis, assessment of the behavior of processes and decision-making on managing the dynamics and trend of complex observed interactions are given. All these examples are oriented for correct application in the study of quantum systems. Considered visual images of analysis results, such as Lyapunov exponents, Tsallis entropy, system memory, Poincare return times, fractal dimensions, and others, can be evaluated for decision making using Visual Thinking. The calculated and presented measuring experimental information can be further applied as input level information for the Recurrent Neural Network of the Deep Learning algorithm.

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